

“THE ROLE OF PPP METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE”

Xasanboyeva Nilufar Mansurovna ¹

¹ Teacher of English language at the secondary school No. 249, Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4766364>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 1st May 2021
Accepted: 5th May 2021
Online: 10th May 2021

KEY WORDS

PPP (presentation, practice, production) method, learning EFL, language structure, scientific point. Teaching speaking skill.

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to describe PPP method of teaching English and understanding the full meaning of the PPP and. Also, the used information in the research provides the students with an opportunity to practice constructing the language structure themselves.

The PPP acronym stands for Presentation, Practice and production. Each letter means a stage of learning process. The first stage is called Presentation, Where the teacher gives explanation on the topic. The practice Stage is the time for the students to use language in a semi control activity. And the production gives the students opportunity to use the language freely.

In fact, the PPP method follows common sense and does not require much advanced pedagogy. Most people have used some variation of the PPP method to learn at some point in their lives. And while the PPP method has its critics, its elegance as a foundation cannot be denied. This is the part of the process that is most passive for the pupil. The teacher presents pupils with new information (e.g. a grammar point, a vocabulary list, etc.). It is important that this information be presented in sufficient detail. The first part of presentation would be introducing the meaning of the new language. This could be a written definition, or a flash

card, or a spoken description of a phrase or idiom's meaning.

PRESENTATION, PRACTICE AND PRODUCTION

The newer but increasingly popular Presentation, Practice and Production (PPP) methodology relies on a three step process to facilitate language acquisition. First, the instructor systematically explains the context, situation and form of the target language lesson in question (Presentation). Then, the students practice this method in a controlled environment through the use of activities and drills (Practice). After such careful reinforcement, students are then given the opportunity to use the language in a freer way to allow expression of their own purpose or meaning (Production). Although it always difficult to compare English learning styles, this approach is useful to many intermediate learners as it presents the student with the material and then provides them with multiple ways to use it in context.

In the world of TEFL there are numerous and various abbreviations and

acronyms – EAP, IELTS, TESOL, to name a few. They can be confusing and don't worry if you don't know what all of them stand for or what they mean yet, but we're going to introduce you to one which you really need to get to know because it's the basis of most TEFL lessons: PPP.

PPP stands for Presentation, Practice and Production. It is a procedure which is widely used in TEFL classrooms when teaching a language structure, especially at lower levels. How does it work? Let's look at an example to see what we mean:

Lesson topic: The Worst Day Ever

Language structure: third conditional

Presentation:

The teacher introduces a character – Mary. Mary is a student who enjoys going out clubbing with her friends. One Thursday night Mary goes out for her friend's birthday and stays out very late. The next morning, she oversleeps and wakes up at 10am. When she wakes up she realises she's going to be late for class. "If I hadn't gone out last night, I wouldn't have overslept", she thinks.

The story continues with many bad things happening to Mary because she went out the night before. Each time something happens, she makes a comment in the third conditional. This story can be presented as an oral story with pictures, a written story or a video. It can be taken from a course book or it can be made up by the teacher.

The teacher then focuses on Mary's comments and the third conditional. The teacher boards the basic form of the structure, elaborates on its meaning and establishes its use. In this way the students are presented with the language structure.

Practice:

The teacher then provides the students with an opportunity to practise constructing the language structure themselves. This is usually a very controlled practice exercise

which focuses on students' accuracy. One way to do this would be for the students to recap Mary's story in their own words, writing down what they remember and working with another student to recreate the story. The whole class then works together until they have the perfect story.

This is also the stage the teacher focuses on issues of pronunciation and lets the students practice producing the structure in sentences.

Production:

The production stage is when students are allowed to come up with sentences with the target structure relating to themselves. They have had time to focus on the form in the Presentation and Practice stages, so this stage is about using the structure in appropriate situations. This is a much freer situation, so though the students may be given prompts, they are free to talk about whichever situation they choose. During this stage the students usually relate the target language to themselves so that the production becomes more personalized and meaningful.

As you can see, this is quite a basic procedure and it's very flexible, meaning that it can be used for a wide range of structures. It is easy to understand why this is the procedure most commonly taught in TEFL courses. However, PPP has been around since the 1960s and upon close examination, we can see there are a few drawbacks to this procedure.

Firstly, PPP is completely teacher-centred. It maintains the traditional status quo of the teacher being the provider of knowledge and the student being the passive recipient. We now know that it is more beneficial in most situations for the student to be actively engaged in the learning situation. The student learns more and better when they are involved in working out meaning or discovering rules and forms themselves.

PPP also assumes that students learn in straight lines, from zero knowledge to a state of comprehension to immediate production. Obviously language learning doesn't take place like that and even if our students are able to produce the target structure accurately during the Production phase, this does not mean that the structure has been learnt or will be used outside the classroom.

Nevertheless, PPP is still one of the most popular procedures around and will probably continue to be so. The fact remains that it has proven effective for so many years that there must be reasons it has stood the test of time. Having said that, though, it is a good idea to mix it up and utilise PPP in a different way or play around with different teaching approaches such as ESA.

Teaching speaking is considered as the "interesting and challenging activity". Indeed, it needs various ways in order to make pupils "active in speaking" during the class. This article would like to present the three phases, namely a PPP (Presentation, Practice, and Production) method in "teaching speaking to

school pupils". The fundamental principles of using this method is that the "pupils are smart and creative". Even though, they are considered as "intelligent and creative", teachers still need to guide or control them to anticipate any errors made by the pupils. Furthermore, it is important for teachers to know when to give "instant correction" in class. When the class is focused on accuracy, teachers can give an "instant correction". On the other hand, when it is focused on "fluency", it is not suggested that teachers give "instant correction" and this may interfere with the goals of activity.

To sum up, The best advantage of the PPP method is changing of stage. It may be difficult to encourage students to do the activity of the three stages. However, I would like use the Practice Stage that suggests semi-control activities for students to use the target language and structure they have learnt. It is really clear that all the Stages of PPP method are effective for traditional teaching and Students do not get bored with the whole class full of the grammar and vocabulary.

References :

1. <https://shaneschools.com/en/what-is-the-ppp-method-of-teaching-english/>
2. <https://www.myenglishlanguage.com/teacher-resources/ppp-technique/>
3. Close R.A. A Reference Grammar for Students of English. – M.: Prosvescheniye.
4. Zaripova R. A. Chet tillar o 'qitish metodikasidan qo'llanma, — T.: o'qituvchi, 2014
5. Gebhard G. J. Teaching English as a Foreign or Second Language, (2nd Ed)- A Teacher Self-Development and Methodology Guide, 2013. University Of Michigan Press..